

A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY ON THE LIVED EXPERIENCE OF ADULTS WITH MOOD DISORDERS

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A Phenomenological Study on the Lived Experience of Adults with Mood Disorders

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Abstract

With concerns still on the level of public awareness and knowledge of mental health, people who are diagnosed with mental health disorders are still having difficulties in receiving appropriate help. There is a need for better understanding and promoting awareness of what people experiencing such challenges are going through and identifying their needs. The study encompasses the lived experiences of individuals with mood disorders, how their diagnosis has changed their lifestyle, their interaction with others, the difficulties they experience, and how they are coping with their condition upon being aware of it. This study uses a qualitative research design and an interpretative phenomenological approach. The study conducted interviews to learn the lived experiences of nine (9) participants, where they could share their experience with changes and how they cope with the said changes. Results found that having a good support system and developing healthy coping mechanisms assist in managing the negative situations that people with mood disorders experience. Through the persistence of being discriminated against, stigmatized, and facing difficulties because of the limitations that accompany the diagnosis. Additionally, maintaining wellness, such as regularly monitoring their medication and lifestyle, can assist in regulating the symptoms and episodes of people with mood disorders.

Keywords: *lifestyle, experiences, coping mechanisms, wellness, limitations, difficulties*

Introduction

People react differently to changes in their lives, with some experiencing denial, secrecy, and reduced confidence. However, most individuals improve their perspectives and ideals over time. A diagnosis helps individuals understand their differences and counteracts shame, isolation, and low self-esteem caused by being perceived as "strange," "bad," or "having a character flaw" (Craddock & Mynors-Wallis, 2014). A mental health diagnosis is a process where mental health assessment tests and physical tests, such as blood work or neurological tests, are used to determine whether an individual has a mental health disorder.

A person with a disability is defined as someone with a physical or mental impairment that limits their regular activities (Department of Health, 2014). An impairment that is connected to having a mental health issue is referred to as psychosocial disability. Psychosocial disability refers to an impairment that is connected to mental health, having more severe symptoms, whereas others merely have mild or moderate symptoms. Due to its indistinctness and the low awareness of mental health, stigma is still very high, making people with psychosocial disabilities feel as if having a comfortable life is difficult (Disability Rights Fund, 2016) for some people, experiencing how difficult it is to look for job opportunities or raising a family is frustrating. Nevertheless, there are people whose experiences are different from others, such as those who have mood disorders that impede them from experiencing things typically. Mood disorders or affective disorders are the outcome of disrupted mood, which are either depressive and hypomania or mania episodes (Ellenbroek, 2016), and have two categories, including Bipolar disorder and Depressive disorder (Sekhon, 2023).

People with disabilities are often looked down upon in society and are discriminated against (Velasco, 2016). Moreover, in today's time, mental health stigma is still prevalent; being assumed that having a disorder means insanity, and being argued that mental illness is something that exists only because you are overreacting and that it is only in your mind. Which in many cases is harmful. Mental health stigma can also be a cause of acquiring mood disorders, especially those who struggle with their mental health (Bharadwaj et al., 2017). This causes scarcity in employment, and despite having stable jobs, people with disabilities may be paid less than non-disabled people (Boman et al., 2015; Thelwell, 2021). This may result in lower self-esteem, reduced hope, difficulties in the workplace, and hardships with social relationships (Borenstein, 2020).

Due to this, the study sought to understand how individuals with mood disorders lived their lives after being diagnosed, as well as whether and how this affected the way they lived their daily lives. Most studies have focused on the specific behaviors that the disorder altered, and most of the studies were narrowed to study specific disorders. The studies about the overall experiences, coping styles, and changes in their lifestyles were insufficient. This was done to aid in expanding knowledge of the condition and to contribute to the literature that will help people become more aware of ways to improve their quality of life.

Research Questions

This qualitative research will be taken to effectively learn about the lived experiences of people with mood disorder after being diagnosed. This aimed to answer the following question:

1. What are the general experiences of individuals with mood disorders post-diagnosis?.
2. What changes do individuals with mood disorders experience post-diagnosis in terms of:
 - 2.1. lifestyle?

- 2.2. interactions with others?
- 2.3. difficulties?
- 3. What coping styles do individuals with mood disorders adapt post diagnosis?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a qualitative research design, which focuses on the structured study of social events occurring in a natural setting, such as their experiences, how individuals act or behave, how institutions arise, and how connections form relationships (Martimianakis et. al, 2015). And the interpretative phenomenological analysis “IPA”, an approach that is “participant-oriented”, which allowed the participants to fully express themselves and their “lived experiences” in an in-depth level.

Participants

The study focused on young adults, aged twenty-one (21) years old to thirty-four (34) years old, with clinically diagnosed mood disorder, and resides in metro manila.

Procedure

The researchers gathered participants by posting an advertisement in Facebook support groups and contacting those who answered.

An informed consent form was given to the participants to be signed as a sign of agreement to be interviewed and to have the interview recorded. A brief orientation was given to the participants on what to expect during the interview, explaining that all information will be confidential, that participants may withdraw their participation at any point of the interview, and that questions regarding their past may be triggering. This was followed by the interview that lasted 10 to 45 minutes, in which participants answered questions regarding their “lived experiences”.

Ethical Considerations

This study follows strict ethical practice and conduct in its progression. Thus, it upholds all procedures ethically. Thus, it recognized the importance of the participant’s well-being which is through the conception of the consent form and its content. All the information provided is within the study’s capabilities and understanding.

- a) Informed consent – the informed consent presents the important details which entail the procedures, risks, benefits, confidentiality, and consent to be recorded for the interview.
- b) Voluntary participation – it is within the participant’s ultimate decision whether they wish to proceed or not with participating in the interview. It is also their right to withdraw at any point before and during the interview if they feel the need to do so.
- c) Confidentiality – all the data gathered from the interview will be secured in privacy by keeping the data in a file that only the researchers have access to.
- d) Anonymity – it is important to establish anonymity to ensure the participant’s safety and privacy. The study did not show any information that could lead to breach in anonymity. The transcript shows only numbers; participant 1, participant 2, to participant 9.
- e) Right to withdraw - the participant has the choice to withdraw from the study at any point that they no longer feel safe or if they no longer wish to participate in the study.
- f) Debriefing - the researchers provided a debriefing session to the participants by explaining how the data that they have provided will be utilized for the study. In light that participants have hesitations, and would like to withdraw their participation, they may do so and their data will not be used.
- g) Triggers - if participants are triggered, the researchers will have had to provide the help they can such as helping the participant perform breathing exercises and other basic mental health first aid that one can provide and will contact professionals immediately if needed.

Results and Discussion

Table of Themes

Table 1. Summary of Themes

Themes	Sub-Themes	Statement
Uncertainty of future	Apprehension for the future	<i>“I think, siguro, after diagnose, mga three months ata, two to three months, hindi ako lumalabas ng bahay. Kasi nasa isip ko, um, like, people with bipolar disorder, violent sila. So, I was afraid na meron akong masaktang tao, gano’n.”</i>
	Apprehension on society’s	<i>‘yun stigmatized- highly stigmatized sa work. Sa family- honestly wala sa family ko</i>

	reaction	<i>ang may alam... hindi nila alam... kasi, uh, hindi... hindi maintindihan, "...nung mismong diagnosis na, surprisingly, ano s'ya, it was relief; as in parang, 'di ko 'yun ine-expect, akala ko mas iiyak ako, pero, may ano s'ya, parang nagkaro 'n ng peace, na, ng relief na okay may- may- may confirmation din na,"</i>
Awareness of condition	Acceptance and relief	<i>Mas naging conscious ako. Mas... pero ang maganda kasi do'n, "mas naging aware ako. Uh, alam ko kung ano yung makakapagpa-trigger sa'kin. Alam kung sa'n ako mas magiging okay, sa'n hinde." "...ano s'ya parang may resistance ako na, um, ayaw ko s'ya, parang hindi ko s'ya ine-embrace. I think 'yung purpose ko, kaya rin ako, parang gusto kong mag-recover, kasi I don't want to have bipolar. " "...ano s'ya parang may resistance ako na, um, ayaw ko s'ya, parang hindi ko s'ya ine-embrace. I think 'yung purpose ko, kaya rin ako, parang gusto kong mag-recover, kasi I don't want to have bipolar. " "Siguro hindi ko pa rin talaga siya fully matanggap now, kasi hindi ko pa rin nahahanap yung uhm coping mechanism ko na really makakahelp sa'kin para ma uh magkaroon ng super laking adjustment para sa sarili ko para hindi maapektuhan yung ibang tao."</i>
	Denial of condition	
	Denial of condition	
Adjustment after the diagnosis	Experiencing stigma	<i>"So, kapag kunyari alam nilang bipolar, parang, 'Ah, kaya s'ya masaya' or 'Energetic s'ya' or 'Ano 'to? Parang loner s'ya?' or a- 'yung himan- 'yung gano'n, parang, um, 'ah, kasi bipolar', parang nakikita nila ako based on that..."</i>
	Psychological	<i>"So an example of that would be if bibigyan ako ng isang business deal that would entail uhm me working 16 hours a day just to make sure the deal pushes through, i say no to that na kasi i value - i value my peace of mind and i value my mental health more " "so ang ginagawa ko nalang is dina-divert ko yung attention ko like, uhm I tried cooking, tapos uh of course taking care of my child, uhm somehow nada-divert pero minsan na ti-trigger niya yung episodes ko. So ayun I tried different things like cooking,uh reading books ganon." "I got more conscious about the food intake na kinakain ko, kasi, of course, dahil sa foods it can trigger, uh, hypomania, so kailangan iwasan yun. Tapos other foods naman that can help you stabilize your mood or, uh, naturally na anti-depressants"</i>
	Physical	
	Social	<i>"yung looking for like support, um, support group, kasi it's different, 'yung kapag friends kasi, parang co-comfort ka lang, pero iba 'yung like people with like really like the similar challenges na nakakaintindi, ayun, so, malaking coping resource ko talaga s'ya." "so a few adjustments was to tell my husband I needed support uhm na i'm going through this, na im rebuilding again so i need your support and patience, and luckily I have a partner that gives that" " Ayun, inaccept ko, tsaka... ayun from ano lang din support din from family ng parents ko malaking ano siya sa'kin."</i>

Summary of Themes

From the data gathered through the semi-structured interviews and analyzed using thematic coding and the IPA data analysis, the study discovered 3 main themes, namely "Uncertainty of Future", "Awareness of Condition", and "Adjustments after the diagnosis". It has been found that people with mood disorders underwent drastic changes and adaptation to cater their lifestyle. The themes explained their experiences regarding their general experiences after diagnosis, changes after their diagnosis in terms of lifestyle; interaction with others' and difficulties as well as the coping mechanisms they used after their diagnosis.

In the theme "uncertainty of future," The participants expressed their apprehension towards the future because of the fear that they might hurt someone because of their disorder. They also expressed their apprehension regarding society as they may receive negative reactions because of the lack of knowledge about their disorder. This shows that mood disorders can affect a person's self-motivation, social engagement, and productivity, which can cause more negative experiences. This was supported by Morris, 2020 and Bickenbach, 2017, who stated that mood disorder causes a decline in social interaction due to the fear that they would not have control over things.

In the theme "awareness of condition," participants shared the adjustment they encountered upon diagnosis, such as optimistic acceptance, which helped them have a greater quality of life (Falvo & Holland, 2017). The participants also shared that because of the side effects of the medication, giving them a hard time adjusting, they pessimistically accepted their diagnosis. However, the participants also shared that the diagnosis felt like proof that they could show people that their disorder is factual and oppose the stigma

they experience.

Lastly, in the theme “Adjustment to diagnosis,” participants shared their experiences in terms of psychological, physical, and social. The participants stated that they needed to prioritize sleep to manage and prevent triggers, and doing activities that divert their attention aided in a much easier adjustment. The participants also stated that for their physical health, they had to monitor their food intake to maintain the stability of their mood, and they often plan what they eat and ensure that their food can boost their positive mood. In terms of social interactions, individuals with mood disorders experience a lack of attention (Fernandes et al., 2018). However, the participants stated that having their families, partners, and people in the same situation as them who act as support helps them adjust, as having social support can encourage a person’s development and growth (Løseth et al., 2022).

Conclusion

The study utilized IPA Data Analysis by Charlick et al. (2015), a thematic analysis used to understand individuals' lived experiences. In this study, it is used to understand the lived experiences of individuals with mood disorders after they were diagnosed and how it affected their lives.

The data gathered was used to describe the general experience of individuals with mood disorders, explain the changes that happened in terms of lifestyle, interaction with others, and difficulties, and identify the coping styles used. The study generated three themes: uncertainty of future, Awareness of condition, and Adjustment to diagnosis.

The first theme, uncertainty of future included the data where the participants stated how their lifestyles were altered regarding interactions. It was found that people with mood disorders had life-changing experiences, such as dropping out of school and being unable to participate in other activities that they used to do, such as outreach programs. It was also discovered that having a balanced diet and getting enough sleep is essential in preventing and avoiding negative effects. Additionally, individuals with mood disorders experience difficulties in maintaining performance in academics due to the medication; they also experience difficulties in finding job opportunities, which leads to refusing to disclose their diagnosis. Individuals with mood disorders experience a decrease in social interaction because of fear that, in light of their condition worsening, they might hurt other people. It was also discovered that having a support system, such as family, partners, friends, and people who experience the same, can aid them in coping with their diagnosis (Løseth et al., 2022).

The theme, awareness of condition, included the data wherein participants stated what difficulties they encountered and how they were able to cope with the adjustments that the participants had to make. Wherein it was stated that individuals with mood disorders endure significant adjustment and adaptability. Despite the difficulties that may come with adapting to medications and their side effects, the discussions emphasize the essential part that acceptance plays in improving the participants' quality of life. Although not always surprising, the diagnosis highlighted the need for adaptation. The participants stated that they adapt through techniques like maintaining a healthy lifestyle, establishing a support system, and participating in activities to divert from triggers. Despite these efforts, future opportunities are still uncertain because of the current restrictions on people with disabilities. The worry is heightened by fears of potential injury to oneself or others, which results in less interactions (Morris, 2020; Bickenbach, 2017). The experiences of persons with mood disorders show adaptability, resilience, and continuous fight to establish stability in the face of change.

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